

Impact of COVID-19 on Export of Mango of Pakistan: A Case Study of Sindh

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Abstract:

This research investigates the Impact of COVID-19 on Export of Mango of Pakistan: A Case study of Sindh. Data were collected from Various farms Syed Farms, Mir Muzaffar Ali Talpur Farm Tando jam and few small growers of Tando Allahyar. According to results most of the contractors are facing multiple problems of labor which is blocked in different areas of Punjab. In this year the production of Mango is superb but due to this pandemics most of the countries where these growers are exporting Mango i.e. Afghanistan, Iran, Australia, USA, UK and other European countries it looks this year nothing will be for exporters of Mango. It was revealed that most of the contractors are suffering due to this pandemics.

Introduction: Pakistani Mangoes are mostly yellow in color when fully ripe, have strong aroma and sweet in taste, no mango of any origin can compete in taste with Pakistani Mango. Anchor Trading Company is well known in the export of Fresh Mangos and is currently exporting to Germany, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Spain, Malaysia, United Arab Emirates, Bahrain, Kuwait, Qatar and Saudi Arabia.

Sindh province is very popular in quality of Mango produced in various areas of Sindh. Sindhri Variety of mango is largely produced in Tando Jam, Tando Allahyar and Mirpur Khas. Export Demand for Sindhri Mango because of its taste and sweetness specially in Australia, USA, UK and Canada every year increasing.

Keywords: Impact of COVID-19, Export of Mango of Pakistan

Major pakistani mango types exported are as follows:

1) SINDHRI MANGO

Leading variety of Sind. Fruit shape ovalish long, size large, skin colour lemon yellow when ripe, pulp colour yellowish cadium, texture fine and firm fibreless, stone medium sized, flavour pleasantly aromatic and taste sweet. We stand top among pakistan's Sindhri Mango Suppliers and Sindhri Mango Exporters.

2) CHAUNSA MANGO

The Chausa or Chaunsa mango of Pakistan is probably one of the worlds' top varieties available. It is an exceptionally sweet mango with a wonderful fragrance and delicious soft, succulent flesh with only the minimum of fiber. We lead the pakistan Chaunsa mango export market as suppliers of Chausa mango and fresh and quality Chausa mango exporters.

3) RED KIND (LAL BADSHAH)

Red king is the name given to a yellow mango with a slight red blush. As the fruit ripens, the yellow becomes deeper. The fruit has a slightly irregular shape. The flesh is quite firm, has some fiber and is sweet without being particularly flavoursome.

4) ANWAR RATOL

Anwar Ratol is popular due to high flavor and abundant of juice. It is smaller in size, heavy pulp full of juice, skin medium thick, pulp is firm and fibreless, can be cut off in slices, flavor very pleasant and very sweet taste. The season of Anwar Ratol starts from mid of July to August.

5) SUNEHRA

Baganphali is the variety of Sindh that is popular due to large volume usually having length of about 14 cm, breadth 9.1 cm and thickness 8.2 cm. Fruit shape is Oval, skin color dark green and become yellowish light green after being matured, surface smooth, sweet taste and heavy pulp and full of tasty juice. Season is extended from July to August.

6) LANGRA

It is the variety of Mango that has splendid demand in Europe and Canada. It is smaller in size, having delicious sweet taste, skin green and thin, attractive fragrance, highly perishing, fibreless, shape a little oval and heavy pulp that looks yellowish brown. The season starts from the mid of June till August.

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Literature Review

UtkuUtkulu and DilekSeymen(2004) employed RCA index to examine competitiveness of Turkish exports with selected countries of EU at sectoral level. In their study Batra and Khan (2005) measured relative export performance at sector and product level between china and India for a period of 2000-20003 using commodity classification at two and six digit level of HS.

Mehmood (2005) used RCA index to measure relative export performance of non-agricultural export commodities at HS-4digit level for 1990-2000. He concluded on the basis of RCA index some commodities are losing market while others are gaining market. Hanif and Jafri (2006) employed RCA index to measure export competitiveness for textile sector of Pakistan. Akhter and Zakir (2008) analyzed export competitiveness of Pakistani footwear exports for a period of 2003-2006 comparing Indian and Chinese exports in similar trade commodities by using RCA index. Shinoj and Mathur (2008) examined Indian agricultural export commodities, using RCA index and RSCA index, with major market players for a period from 1991 to 2004 and concluded that some of their exports are losing global markets after economic reforms.

Akhter and Sharif (2009) examined competitiveness of Pakistan's fruit exports (dates, mangoes and oranges) by employing RCA index and RXA index, comparing with major exporters of similar commodities.

Riaz(2012) used Balassa RCA index to calculate competitiveness a wide range of Pakistan agricultural exports commodities. To measure competitiveness of Pakistan's agricultural export commodities, Hassan (2013) employed RCA index for a period from 2001 to 2010 and concluded that rice exhibited very strong competitiveness in world export market.

III. Challenges and Opportunities for Pakistan s' Mango Crop

In the current situation of COVID-19 has impact on export of Mango in Pakistan. Though production became almost double during the period under study (2020), due to this pandemic situation and unavailability of labor from various parts of south Punjab. There is opportunity for the local labor of Sindh, most of the mango farmers to arrange training for the local labor.

Methodology

Data were collected from various farms i.e. Nadeem Shah, Goopang fam, Imdad Nizamani Farm and SAU Tando jam Orchard. Data were analyzed by using SPSS-21 softawre.

Results: Maximum care is put into production of these mangoes which comes with long experience and special tradition of cultivating and supplying mangoes. We export Pakistani Mangoes to USA, UK, CANADA, SAUDI ARABIA, OMAN, KUWAIT, BAHRAIN, FRANCE, AUSTRALIA, MALAYSIA, DUBAI, HONG KONG, GERMANY, JAPAN, UAE and Europe. Pakistan is amongst the largest producers of the world's best mango which is liked all over the Globe for its aroma, color and taste. The main types of the Pakistani Mango Rawaayat deals in are Sindhri, Chaunsa, Anwer Ratol and Dosehri.

The rapid growth of mango production in Pakistan in past few years is attributable to its expansion into new growing regions along with the implementation of modern field practices incorporating irrigation schemes, flowering management, etc. Demand of Pakistani mangoes in Canada, USA and UK has doubled over the past few years.

Source: customs today

Valuable foreign exchange worth \$80 million has been generated so far through the export of mangoes. Compared to the last year, there has been a substantial increase both in volume and revenue this year. The production of mango was 1.3 million tonnes and export volume stood at 85,000 tonnes last year, while the production of mango during the current year was 1.5 million tonnes,” Waheed Ahmed informed.

“Last year the production of mango was 1.3 million tonnes and export volume stood at 85,000 tonnes, while this year mango production was 1.5 million tonnes,” he added.

Waheed credits the considerable augmentation in export volume of mango to energetic and enthusiastic marketing which carried mango promotions in twenty-five different countries under the umbrella of joint sponsorship of Pakistani foreign missions and PFVA.

Throughout the promotions, Pakistani mango was originated uniquely and the participators in these events celebrated rich taste and distinct aroma of the mango fruit.

Conclusions:

The current research investigates the Mango export oriented problems during the COVID-19 pandemic in Sindh province. Mango is one the most prominent fruits commercially grown. Furthermore, Pakistan is the fourth leading producer of mangoes in the world. The total area under mango cultivation is 167.5 thousand hectares with the production of 1732 thousand tones of Pakistani mangoes, grown all over the districts of Punjab, Sindh and KPK. Punjab has the primary share in mango production; leading by 67% meanwhile Sindh and KPK contribute 24% and 1% to this production, respectively. These mangoes are treated per international standards packaged in temperature-controlled environment for consignment. To keep away from pests and bacteria, the mangoes undergo further processes.

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